

D1.1

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

HiSeedTech

D1.1

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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Abstract

The Data Management Plan (DMP) of the S3E project outlines how the project data will be handled during the lifetime of the project.

Keywords

S3E, deep tech, science-based, entrepreneurship, technology commercialization, innovation ecosystem, southern Europe, data management plan.

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Nature of the deliverable

DMP

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

S3E Partners:

Table of contents

1	Executive summary	6
2	Introduction.....	7
2.1	Zenodo	7
2.2	F6S.....	8
2.3	Eventbrite	8
3	Privacy Policy	9
3.1	Detailed Privacy Policy.....	9
3.1.1	Policy scope	9
3.1.2	Personal data that this website collects provided by you and how we use it.....	9
3.1.3	How we store your personal data.....	10
3.1.4	How long we will keep your personal data for.....	11
3.1.5	Cookies and third-party cookies	11
3.1.6	Data breaches	14
3.1.7	Your rights as data subject with respect to your personal data.....	15
3.1.8	Right of access.....	15
3.1.9	Right to rectification	15
3.1.10	Time limits for compliance with your rights as data subject.....	16
3.1.11	Data controller and contact details	17
3.1.12	How to complain.....	17
3.1.13	Changes to our privacy policy.....	17
	ANNEX – Application Forms	18
	S3E Start application form	19
	For researchers	19
	For TTOS	25
	S3E Charge application form	27
	S3E Reverse	29
	For challengers.....	29

List of tables

Table 1. Necessary cookies	12
Table 2. Statistic cookies	13
Table 3. Marketing cookies	14

Abbreviations

AUS	Australo Interinnov Marketing Lab SL
DoA	Description of Action
DMP	Data management plan
EPLO	The Institute for Sustainable Development is an initiative of the European Public Law Organization
HST	HiSeedTech
IDI	International Development Ireland Limited
S3E	Southern European Entrepreneurship
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
WP	Work Package
TTO	Technology Transfer Officer

1 Executive summary

The **S3E project** ambition is to develop an engine of growth that will contribute to **improve the connectedness and efficiency of the entrepreneurship ecosystems in Southern European countries**. The proposed project will focus on the **acceleration of deep tech projects**, start-ups, and SMEs that, by providing solutions towards a more sustainable society and economy, can impact social development and economic growth in these countries and contribute to the timely achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)¹, in line with the EU Green Deal, the EU Digital Agenda and the Recovery Plan for Europe.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) provides the framework required to ensure compliant and safe operation of the **S3E project** by defining policies and guidelines for all the stages of data collection. It addresses issues such as collection of data, data set identifiers and descriptions, standards and metadata used in the project, data sharing, property rights and privacy protection, and long-term preservation and re-use, complying with national and EU legislation.

The DMP itself is a living document that is updated periodically if required.

¹ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

2 Introduction

The DMP establishes the Data Management strategy and planning to be defined within the S3E Project. It incorporates details on the data management process, including policies and guidelines for:

- data collection and processing.
- identification of possible ethical and/or legal issues; and
- definition of all processes and instruments for regular conformity assessment and risk mitigation measures.

The DMP addresses issues such as collection of data and privacy protection, and long-term preservation and re-use, complying with national and EU legislation.

The following is a listing of resources that we use in the data management process.

2.1 Zenodo

S3E facilitates an online repository to manage and publish material with different access permissions, including peer-reviewed publications and other types of resources generated. The project relies on Zenodo –part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)– to deposit all publications.

- **S3E Start Open Call #1 Text**
The document is published on <https://zenodo.org/record/7457990#.Y6SDui8qLfl>
- **S3E Start Guidelines for Applicants**
The document is published on <https://zenodo.org/record/7457990#.Y6SEii8qK2t>
- **S3E Experts Expression of Interest text**
The document is published on <https://zenodo.org/record/7377769#.Y5xQQC8qLfl>
- **S3E Charge: Open call text #1**
The document is published on <https://zenodo.org/record/7330565#.Y6SWoS8qLfK>
- **S3E Charge Guidelines for Applicants**
The document is published on <https://zenodo.org/record/7330565#.Y6SWoS8qLfK>
- **S3E Reverse Open Call #1 text**
The document is published on <https://zenodo.org/record/7324130#.Y6SXyy8qLfK>
- **S3E Reverse Guidelines for Applicants**
The document is published on <https://zenodo.org/record/7324130#.Y6SXyy8qLfK>

2.2 F6S

The F6S platform is the entry point for all proposals' submissions to S3E Open Calls, which is directly linked from S3E website (<https://south3e.eu/>). Submissions received by any other channel and after the open call deadline will be automatically discarded.

Evaluators and Mentors are subjected to NDAs before assessing confidential information shared by individuals, teams and organizations involved in the S3E programs.

Applications forms are available below:

S3E START

- For researchers: <https://www.f6s.com/south3e-start-for-researchers/apply>
- For TTOs: <https://www.f6s.com/south3e-start-for-tech-transfer-offices/apply>

S3E CHARGE

- For growth startups: <https://www.f6s.com/s3e-charge/apply>

S3E REVERSE

- For corporates and public organizations: <https://www.f6s.com/s3e-reverse/apply>

In the Annex we have attached the screenshots of the relevant data we collect.

The privacy policy of F6S available at <https://www.f6s.com/privacy-policy>

2.3 Eventbrite

The Eventbrite is the entry for all registrations on the information sessions of the S3E: <https://www.eventbrite.es/o/south3e-the-engine-for-south-european-deep-tech-55417867473>

The privacy policy of Eventbrite available at:

https://www.eventbrite.com/support/articles/en_US/Troubleshooting/eventbrite-privacy-policy?lg=en_US

3 Privacy Policy

The S3E project is committed to protecting participant's privacy and is developing technology that provides the most powerful and safe online experience.

This Statement of Privacy applies to the Website of the Horizon Europe S3E project (Grant Agreement 101072135) and governs data collection and usage.

The Website falls under the responsibility of the S3E Consortium and is concerned with the dissemination and exchange of information about the research conducted during the project and the outcome of this work.

3.1 Detailed Privacy Policy

The following privacy policy is publicly available on the S3E website (<https://south3e.eu/privacy-policy/>):

3.1.1 Policy scope

This Privacy Policy applies to this Website – www.south3e.eu – and does so regardless of whether you use a computer, mobile phone, tablet, TV, or other device.

3.1.2 Personal data that this website collects provided by you and how we use it

Unless stated otherwise in detail in the relevant sections of the Website, Personal Data generated from the use of our Website is processed as follows:

- **Contact via electronic mail (e-mail)**

Should you choose to communicate with us via an email, we invite you to provide your name, as well your mailing address. Please note that your name and mailing address is the only data we collect required for the specified purpose. Without this information we are unable to answer your message and address it to you personally. The legal basis for processing Personal Data for the purposes set out in this Section 2 is art. 6(1)(b) of GDPR as the processing is necessary for the response to requests from the interested party.

- **Social Media**

Some of our webpages use social plug-ins from other organizations (such as Twitter's retweet function). These other organizations may receive and use personal data about your visit to our sites or apps. If you browse our website or view content on our apps, information they collect may be connected to your account on their site. For more information on how these organizations use personal data, please read their privacy policies.

- **Site visitation tracking**

We use Google Analytics (GA) to track user interaction and for statistical reasons. We use this data to determine the number of people using our site, to better understand how they find and use our web pages and to see their journey through the website.

Although GA records data such as your geographical location, device, internet browser and operating system, none of this information personally identifies you to us. Your computer's IP address is anonymized by GA services and cannot be used to personally identify you. We consider Google to be a third party.

GA makes use of cookies, details of which can be found on Google's developer guides. For your information, our website uses the analytics.js implementation of GA. Disabling cookies on your internet browser will stop GA from tracking any part of your visit to pages within this website.

3.1.3 How we store your personal data

If you submit your contact details via the preferred email message, the only personal data that will be stored is the name and email address we receive from you. We will not share your contact details with no one and will be securely stored by S3E with access only by authorized personnel. This is currently the only occasion where personal data will be stored by this Website.

We utilize state-of-the-art technology to store your data. The following safeguards are used, for example, to protect your personal data from misuse or any form of unauthorized processing:

- Access to personal data is restricted to a limited number of authorized persons for the stated purposes.
- The IT systems used for processing data are technically isolated from other systems to prevent unauthorized access and hacking.
- Access to these IT systems is constantly monitored to detect and prevent misuse in the early stages.

3.1.4 How long we will keep your personal data for

We will keep your personal information only for as long as it is relevant and useful for the intended purpose for which it was originally collected, or as required by law.

3.1.5 Cookies and third-party cookies

Cookies are small text files that can be used by websites to make a user's experience more efficient. Our website does not collect any cookies apart from the necessary ones.

You reserve the right to set up your browser to warn you before accepting cookies, or you can simply set it to refuse them, although you may not have access to all the features of this website if you do so. See your browser 'help' button for how you can do this. You do not need to have Cookies on to use or navigate through many parts of this Website. Remember that if you use different computers in different locations, you will need to ensure that each browser is adjusted to suit your Cookie preferences.

This website uses cookies. We use cookies to ensure that we give you the best experience on our website. Please make sure to check out our Terms of Use and Privacy Policy, which govern the use of this site.

Cookies are small text files that can be used by websites to make a user's experience more efficient. The law states that we can store cookies on your device if they are strictly necessary for the operation of this site. For all other types of cookies, we need your permission. This site uses different types of cookies. Some cookies are placed by third party services that appear on our pages. You can at any time change or withdraw your consent from the Cookie Declaration on our website.

Learn more about who we are, how you can contact us and how we process personal data in our Privacy Policy. Cookie declaration last updated on 30/11/22 by [Cookiebot](#):

Necessary (8)

Necessary cookies help make a website usable by enabling basic functions like page navigation and access to secure areas of the website. The website cannot function properly without these cookies.

Name	Provider	Purpose	Expiry	Type
CONSENT [x2]	Google YouTube	Used to detect if the visitor has accepted the marketing category in the cookie banner. This cookie is necessary for GDPR-compliance of the website.	2 years	HTTP Cookie
CookieConsent	Cookiebot	Stores the user's cookie consent state for the current domain	1 year	HTTP Cookie
unicodeAI.css	south3e.eu	Determines which device is used by the visitor - This allows the website to adjust to the optimal resolution for that specific device.	Session	HTTP Cookie
unicodeAI.images	south3e.eu	Determines which device is used by the visitor - This allows the website to adjust to the optimal resolution for that specific device.	Session	HTTP Cookie
unicodeAI.screen	south3e.eu	Determines which device is used by the visitor - This allows the website to adjust to the optimal resolution for that specific device.	Session	HTTP Cookie
webp_lossless_supported	south3e.eu	Used to implement WebP format pictures onto the website.	Persistent	HTML Local Storage
webp_lossy_supported	south3e.eu	Used to implement WebP format pictures onto the website.	Persistent	HTML Local Storage

Table 1. Necessary cookies

Statistics (2)

Statistic cookies help website owners to understand how visitors interact with websites by collecting and reporting information anonymously.

Name	Provider	Purpose	Expiry	Type
_ga	Google	Registers a unique ID that is used to generate statistical data on how the visitor uses the website.	399 days	HTTP Cookie
ga#	Google	Used by Google Analytics to collect data on the number of times a user has visited the website as well as dates for the first and most recent visit.	399 days	HTTP Cookie

Table 2. Statistic cookies

Marketing (12)

Marketing cookies are used to track visitors across websites. The intention is to display ads that are relevant and engaging for the individual user and thereby more valuable for publishers and third-party advertisers.

Name	Provider	Purpose	Expiry	Type
VISITOR_INFO1_LIVE	YouTube	Tries to estimate the users' bandwidth on pages with integrated YouTube videos.	179 days	HTTP Cookie
YSC	YouTube	Registers a unique ID to keep statistics of what videos from YouTube the user has seen.	Session	HTTP Cookie
yt.innertube::nextId	YouTube	Registers a unique ID to keep statistics of what videos from YouTube the user has seen.	Persistent	HTML Local Storage
yt.innertube::requests	YouTube	Registers a unique ID to keep statistics of what videos from YouTube the user has seen.	Persistent	HTML Local Storage
ytidb::LAST_RESULT_ENTRY_KEY	YouTube	Stores the user's video player preferences using embedded YouTube video	Persistent	HTML Local Storage

Name	Provider	Purpose	Expiry	Type
yt-remote-cast-available	YouTube	Stores the user's video player preferences using embedded YouTube video	Session	HTML Local Storage
yt-remote-cast-installed	YouTube	Stores the user's video player preferences using embedded YouTube video	Session	HTML Local Storage
yt-remote-connected-devices	YouTube	Stores the user's video player preferences using embedded YouTube video	Persistent	HTML Local Storage
yt-remote-device-id	YouTube	Stores the user's video player preferences using embedded YouTube video	Persistent	HTML Local Storage
yt-remote-fast-check-period	YouTube	Stores the user's video player preferences using embedded YouTube video	Session	HTML Local Storage
yt-remote-session-app	YouTube	Stores the user's video player preferences using embedded YouTube video	Session	HTML Local Storage
yt-remote-session-name	YouTube	Stores the user's video player preferences using embedded YouTube video	Session	HTML Local Storage

Table 3. Marketing cookies

3.1.6 Data breaches

We will report any unlawful data breach of your data within 72 hours of the breach if it is apparent that personal data stored in an identifiable manner has been stolen.

3.1.7 Your rights as data subject with respect to your personal data

Under the General Data Protection Regulation [Articles 15-21], you have a number of important rights free of charge. In summary, those include rights to:

3.1.8 Right of access

You have the right to be aware and verify the legitimate nature of the processing. So, you have the right to access your personal data and receive additional information about how we process it.

3.1.9 Right to rectification

You have the right to study, correct, update or modify your personal data by contacting S3E at s3e@australo.org.

Right to erasure (Right to be forgotten)

You have the right to request deletion of your personal data when we process it on your consent or in order to protect our legitimate interests. In all other cases (such as, where there is a contract, obligation to process personal data legally required, or public interest), this right is subject to specific restrictions or shall not exist, as the case may be.

Right to restriction of processing

You have the right to request a restriction of the processing of your personal data in the following cases: (a) when the accuracy of the personal data is contested and until the accuracy is verified (b) when you oppose the deletion of your personal data and request the restriction of their use instead, c) when personal data are not needed for processing purposes, they are however required for the establishment, exercise, or defense of legal claims, and (d) when you object to the processing and the decision on your objection to processing is pending.

Right to object to processing

You have the right to object at any time to the processing of your personal data where, as described above, the processing is based on the legitimate interests we pursue as data controllers, as well as, for the purposes of direct marketing and consumer profiling, if applicable.

Right to data portability

You have the right to receive your personal data free of charge in a format that allows you to access, use, and edit them with commonly used editing methods. You also have the right to ask us, in case it is technically feasible, to transmit the data directly to another controller. Your right to do so exists for the data you have provided to us and is processed by automated means based on your consent or for the execution of a relevant contract.

Right to withdraw your consent

In cases where processing is based on your consent, you have the right to withdraw it without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent prior to its withdrawal.

If you would like to exercise any of those rights, please:

- contact us using our Contact details below,
- let us have enough information to identify you,
- let us have proof of your identity and address, and
- let us know the information to which your request relates.

3.1.10 Time limits for compliance with your rights as data subject

We make every effort to comply with all requests within 30 days. However, this period may be extended for reasons relating to the specific right or complexity of your request.

3.1.11 Data controller and contact details

The data controller of this website is:

AUSTRALO INTERINNOV MARKETING LAB SL (“AUSTRALO”), a Private Company established in Spain.

Whose registered office is at:

CL POMPEU, FABRA 1, 2-4, CASTELLDEFELS (BARCELONA) 08860, Spain, VAT number: ESB67553677.

All questions, comments and requests regarding this Privacy Policy may be also addressed to the following Contact details to contact@australo.org or post address to our Company.

3.1.12 How to complain

We hope that we can resolve any query or concern you raise about our use of your Data However, if you believe that we have not responded in an appropriate manner to your complaints or concerns, the General Data Protection Regulation also gives you the right to lodge a complaint with your local data protection or supervisory authority, in particular in the European Union (or European Economic Area) state where you work, normally live or where any alleged infringement of data protection laws occurred.

3.1.13 Changes to our privacy policy

This privacy policy may change from time to time in line with legislation or industry developments. We will not explicitly inform our clients or website users of these changes. Instead, we recommend that you check this page occasionally for any policy changes.

ANNEX – Application Forms

S3E Start application form

For researchers

Questions

PRINCIPAL APPLICANT

1 Applicant name: *

2 Project name: *

3 Affiliation: *

4 E-mail: *

5 Contact:

6 Country: *

7 Will you participate in the S3E Start program and sessions? *

Yes

No

TEAM MEMBERS/ CO-APPLICANTS

Please identify the (other) team members that will actively participate in the S3E Start and, as so, will attend the sessions/meetings of the Program. The team should have 2 to 5 researchers.

Member 1

8 **Name: ***

9 **Email Address: ***

10 **Affiliation: ***

11 **Affiliation Country: ***

Member 2

12 **Name:**

13 **Email Address:**

14 **Affiliation:**

15 **Affiliation Country:**

Member 3

16 **Name:**

17 **Email Address:**

18 **Affiliation:**

19 **Affiliation Country:**

Member 4:

20 **Name:**

21 **Email Address:**

22 **Affiliation:**

23 **Affiliation Country:**

Member 5

24 **Name:**

25 **Email Address:**

26 **Affiliation:**

27 **Affiliation Country:**

TECHNOLOGY AND / OR SCIENCE

28 **Technology and / or science field: ***

Agricultural sciences ▼

29 **The Sustainable Development Goals the project aims to address: ***

- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> No Poverty | <input type="checkbox"/> Zero Hunger | <input type="checkbox"/> Good Health and Well-being |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Quality Education | <input type="checkbox"/> Gender Equality | <input type="checkbox"/> Clean water and sanitation |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Affordable and clean energy | <input type="checkbox"/> Decent work and economic growth | <input type="checkbox"/> Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Reduced inequalities | <input type="checkbox"/> Sustainable Cities and Communities | <input type="checkbox"/> Responsible Consumption and Production |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Climate Action | <input type="checkbox"/> Life Below Water | <input type="checkbox"/> Life On Land |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions | <input type="checkbox"/> Partnerships for the Goals | |

30 **Describe the technology and/or scientific discoveries, in terms of what it does rather than the technical details on how it works (maximum 7,500 characters, including spaces). ***

7500

31 **Describe what is the uniqueness and / or innovativeness of what you are proposing (maximum 7,500 characters, including spaces). ***

ssss 7496

32 **Describe the current status of development and outline the main tasks required for the next stage of development (maximum 5,000 characters, including spaces). ***

5000

33 Describe a potential application that can be enabled by the proposed technology / scientific discovery (maximum 5,000 characters, including spaces). *

5000

34 What is the team's motivation to attend the Program? (maximum 3,000 characters, including spaces) *

3000

35 Would you like to subscribe to our newsletter? *

- Yes
- No

36 How did you hear about S3E Start Program?

For TTOS

APPLICANT

1 Applicant name: *

2 E-mail: *

3 Host Institution: *

4 Job Title: *

5 Contact:

6 LinkedIn *

7 Host Institution Country: *

8 What is your motivation to attend the S3E Start Program? (Maximum 5,000 characters, including spaces). *

5000

9 Brief biography (Maximum 5,000 characters, including spaces). *

5000

10 The Host Institution must confirm its support to the technology transfer officer. The complete wording should be printed on paper with the official letterhead of the HI, blue-inked signed, stamped, and dated by the Institution's legal representative. In case it is digitally signed, there is no need to stamp it. Proposals that do not include this institutional statement may be declared inadmissible. Please upload it here. (Max file size 30MB.) *

[Choose a File](#)

11 Would you like to subscribe to our newsletter? *

- Yes
- No

12 How did you hear about S3E Start Program?

S3E Charge application form

Questions

PRINCIPAL APPLICANT

1 Company Short name: *

2 Company Full official name (As Registered) *

3 Country the start-up is established in: *

4 Reg. / VAT no: *

5 Company website: *

6 Main Contact name: *

7 Main Contact email: *

TEAM MEMBERS/ CO-APPLICANTS:

Please identify the team members that will actively participate in the S3E Charge and, as so, will attend the sessions/meetings of the Program.

8 Please provide 1) Name 2) Position and 3) Email Address for all the members *

TEAM MEMBERS/ CO-APPLICANTS:

Please identify the team members that will actively participate in the S3E Challenge and, as so, will attend the sessions/meetings of the Program.

8 Please provide 1) Name 2) Position and 3) Email Address for all the members *

TECHNOLOGY AND / OR SCIENCE

9 Technology and / or science field: *

10 The SDGs the project aims to address: *

11 Please provide a short description of your start-up and its activities *

12 Please upload a video presentation of a pitch deck focused on sustaining the value proposition for your proposed product, service or process concept (maximum time 7 minutes). (Max file size 30MB.)

13 Please provide a written business case characterizing your product concept and the opportunity (market need), the technology and the development plan, intellectual property status and strategy, the market and the first customer, the competitive advantage and the funding needs *

14 In what way do you believe your technologies can address any of the SDGs of the call defined above? *

15 What is the team motivation to attend the Program? *

16 Would you like to subscribe to our newsletter? *

17 How did you hear about S3E Start Program? *

S3E Reverse

For challengers

Questions

PRINCIPAL APPLICANT

1 Company Short name: *

2 Company Full official name (As Registered): *

3 Country: *

4 Reg. / VAT no: *

5 Company website: *

TEAM MEMBERS/ CO-APPLICANTS:

Please identify the team members that will actively participate in the S3E Reserve and, as so, will attend the sessions/meetings of the Program.

6 Challenge Organisation Coordinator* (Main Organisation Contact) Name: Position: E-mail address *

7 CHALLENGE TITLE *

8 CHALLENGE DESCRIPTION *

200

TECHNOLOGY AND / OR SCIENCE

9 Technology and / or science field: *

Select One ▾

CONTEXT OF USE

10 Where it can be used, what kind of problems this challenge creates. How do you address it today (if you do) *

TECHNICAL KEY CRITERIA, REQUIREMENTS, AND CONSTRAINTS

11 Are there any key criteria, restrictions, constraints you would like to add? *

BENEFITS THAT A SOLUTION WILL BRING TO THE ORGANISATION.

12 How a solution to this challenge will help your organisation *

POTENTIAL COMMERCIAL IMPACT OF FINDING A SOLUTION FOR THE CHALLENGE.

13 If this challenge is addressed, will it have commercial opportunities for your organisation? *

RELEVANT SDGs

14 The SDGs the project aims to address: *

- | | | |
|---|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> No Poverty (SDG 1) | <input type="checkbox"/> Zero Hunger (SDG 2) | <input type="checkbox"/> Good Health and Well-Being (SDG 3) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Quality Education (SDG 4) | <input type="checkbox"/> Gender Equality (SDG 5) | <input type="checkbox"/> Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Industry Innovation and Infrastructure (SDG 9) | <input type="checkbox"/> Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10) | |